

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15769640

Environmental Effect of Ozone Depletion and its Interactions with Climate Change

Lead Author:

Prof. Okeke Gerald Ndubuisi
(Professor of Climate Change & Environmental Sustainability)
FNisafetyE, FISPON, etc.
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.

2nd Author: Associate Professor Cynthia Amaka OBIORAH PhD
Centre for Occupational Health Safety and Environment,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
cynthia.obiora@cohseuniport.edu.ng

Engr. Prof. Theophilus Aku Ugah
Engineer/Environmentalist/Oil & Gas Professional
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.
theogah2004@gmail.com.

Engr. Cletus Onyemhese Agbakhamen
Email ID: cletus.agbakhamen@chevron.com; ceestrides@gmail.com
Phone number: +2348039760095

Engr. Prof. Sony Emeka Ali
(Professor of Civil Engineering & Project Management)
FNSE, FNICE, FNisafetyE, FNIStructE.
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.

Dr. Omatseyione Nesiana
Health Safety & Environmentalist/Geologist/Oil & Gas Professional
Email: otseyione@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The earth has its own blanket which is responsible for saving it from ultra violet rays, these rays if allowed to reach the earth would cause severe damage to living things especially the humans. We used the archival research to base our research discussion and findings. The ozone is responsible for managing the rays and its ability to resist and control or reduce the rays can be made less effective due to the activities of mankind, this is called ozone depletion. And using content analysis, we were able to make reviews on ozone layer, its depletion, causes of its depletion, and the effects of the depletion and recommended a possible way out. The study found out the effects of ozone depletion has serious consequences or effects on human health, plants, ecosystems, biogeochemical cycles and earth's environment. The study also established the solutions to ozone layer depletion to include: avoid products that results in ozone depletion, advocate for ozone protection, and speak to your family, friends, colleagues and encourage them to drive less, eat local, to dispose of fire extinguishers and air conditioning units containing. Based on the findings of the study it is hereby recommended that, the consumption of gases dangerous to the ozone-layer due to their content or manufacturing process should be avoided. It is also recommended that cleaning products that are harmful to the environment should be avoided this is because many cleaning products contain solvents and substances corrosive, but you can replace these dangerous substances with non-toxic products such as vinegar and bicarbonate.

Keywords: Ozone, depletion, earth, temperatures, heat waves, landslides, floods, greenhouse gases, global warming.

INTRODUCTION

The Long-term fluctuations in climate that have taken place over decades, centuries, or longer have been generally called climate change. All living things Earth are now aware of climate change through the consequences of climate change through multiple disasters like intense rain, high temperatures, heat waves, landslides, floods, and so on. Global warming has raised interest in climate change studies during the last few decades. Many of the factors influencing climate change have been identified on Earth. Among many factors, greenhouse gases have been recognized as the primary contributors to increasing global warming. Scientists have also been searching for the causes of climate change above the surface of the Earth, especially space-related factors. Therefore, the researchers have been searching for the factors from the atmosphere. The atmosphere has been described as a blanket of gases that surrounds the Earth. It has been made up of a mixture of gases, mostly nitrogen, oxygen, argon, and carbon dioxide. It has reached over 500 km above the surface of the planet (Rozema & Blokker, 2015).

The stratosphere is one of the atmospheric layers, lying between 12 to 50 kilometers above the Earth's surface, and contains the natural ozone (O₃) layer. Ozone has been identified as a gas made up of three oxygen atoms (O₃). The ozone layer in the stratosphere has been absorbing most of the sun's ultraviolet (UV) radiation. A hole in the ozone layer over Antarctica has been discovered by the British Antarctic Survey's Joe Farman, Brian Gardiner, and Jonathan Shanklin, which was announced in 1985. The Antarctic ozone hole is usually an event where the ozone concentration over Antarctica often becomes significantly depleted during the Southern Hemisphere's springtime (September-November). This depletion is basically caused by human-made chemicals called chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), which are commonly used in air conditioners, refrigerators, fire extinguishers, aerosols, and other goods. Usually, these goods are referred to as ozone-depleting substances (ODS). Usually, the ozone is measured in units often called the Dobson Units (DU).

Dobson Unit has been referred to as the thickness of the ozone layer in a vertical column from the surface to the top of the atmosphere, a quantity called the "total column ozone amount". Before 1979, total column ozone values over Antarctica had never depleted below 220 Dobson Units (DU). The global mean ozone concentration in the upper atmosphere is around 300 DU, with regional variations ranging from 230 to 500 DU.

Ozone depletion has referred to two phenomena: a decrease in the overall amount of ozone in the stratosphere and a drop in ozone on the pole side during the long springtime (Rozema, & Blokker, 2015). The scientists have made awareness about the ozone hole to governments, and have made efforts to stop

it. As a result, Mostafa Kamal Tolba, head of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), brought the nations together for a global agreement to safeguard the stratospheric ozone layer. This agreement was signed in 1987 and has called the Montreal Protocol, which has gradually ceased the manufacturing and use of ozone-depleting substances (ODS). It has been ratified by 197 countries, making it the first treaty in the history of the United Nations to achieve universal ratification. The protocol has been successful in reducing the atmospheric concentration of key ODS, such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and halons, by over 90% since its implementation (Rozema, & Blokker, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

The depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer, primarily caused by human activities releasing ozone-depleting substances, poses significant environmental and health risks, including increased ultraviolet radiation reaching the Earth's surface, which can lead to skin cancer, cataracts, and damage to marine and terrestrial ecosystems. Furthermore, the complex interactions between ozone depletion and climate change exacerbate these issues, as changes in climate can influence ozone layer recovery and vice versa. Despite international efforts to reduce ozone-depleting substances through agreements like the Montreal Protocol, the ongoing impacts of ozone depletion and its interplay with climate change necessitate continued research to inform effective policy and mitigation strategies, ensuring the protection of both human health and the environment.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine environmental effect of ozone depletion and its interactions with climate change. Specifically the study seeks to:

1. Examine the causes of ozone depletion.
2. Investigate the effect of ozone depletion.
3. Assess the Solutions to ozone layer depletion.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the causes of ozone depletion?
2. What are the effects of ozone layer depletion?
3. What are the measures taken to curb ozone layer depletion?

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focuses on the causes, effect and, the Solutions to ozone layer depletion. While the limitations of the study include:

1. Due to time and resource constraints, the research does not involve primary data collection or fieldwork.
2. Second, due to weather difference some findings may be more applicable to other regions.

Significance of the Study

1. This study will enhance the understanding of the complex interactions between ozone depletion and climate change.
2. Similarly, the study provides insights for policymakers to develop effective strategies addressing both issues.
3. Supports ecosystem protection: By exploring impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity.
4. Protects human health: By examining effects on human health and well-being.

By exploring these aspects, this study can contribute to the development of more effective environmental policies and mitigation strategies.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Ozone Layer: Ozone is a natural gas that is present in the atmosphere; it is the three-atom allotrope of oxygen. Ozone Layer Depletion refers to the thinning or reduction in the quality of the Ozone layer in the Earth's Stratosphere. Ozone layer depletion is a thermodynamically unstable gas that readily decomposes into molecular oxygen. Normally, a dynamic equilibrium exists between the production and

decomposition of ozone molecules. Ozone layer depletion occurs when this balance of stratospheric ozone is tipped in favour of destruction.

Formation of Ozone: Life on earth began 3.5 billion years ago, first photosynthetic release of oxygen was about 2.5 billion years ago. They were restricted to underwater environment where they are relatively protected from unfiltered Ultra Violet radiation. However, until half a billion years ago organisms could not able to inhabit on land. Released oxygen of the photosynthesis gradually form ozone which was concentrated in stratosphere (12-50 km in altitude) and prevents the penetration of UV radiation (McMichael, 1993 as cited in McMichael, 2003, pp. 159). Finally, about 400 million years ago the aquatic plants were able to migrate into now protected atmosphere (McMichael, 2003, pp. 159).

UV radiation : UV radiation can be divided into UVA (315-400nm), UVB (280-315 nm) and UVC (< 280nm) (Horneck, 1995 cited in McMichael, 2003, pp. 162). UVA has highest skin penetration but less harmful but UVB is harmful as it causes changes to the DNA molecules and leads to cancer, UVC is the most carcinogenic radiation with highest energy but it is difficult for UVC to penetrate through the epidermis. Whole of UVC and 90% of UVB are absorbed by the stratospheric ozone and less harmful UVA passes through atmosphere. Ambient UVB availability depends on factors such as stratospheric ozone levels, solar elevation, regional elevation, altitude of the individual, cloud cover and reflective surfaces such as water and snow (McMichael, 2003).

Causes of Ozone Layer Depletion

There have been several concerns about ozone depletion. The problems and causes associated with ozone depletion arise from human activities. Unlike pollution which has several causes, there is one specific chemical compound that is responsible for the breakdown of the ozone layer.

These chemical compounds are present in many industrial manufactured products and aerosols. Nonetheless, since the discovery of ozone depletion, the Montreal Protocol was established to regulate the manufacture and use of these chemical compounds. We shall discuss below is the detailed account of the chemicals responsible for the ozone layer depletion.

1. Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs)

Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) have been considered to be the primary cause for the ozone layer depletion. They are basically from our everyday Industrial products which includes; solvents, soaps, spray aerosols, insulating foams, 'take-away' containers and cooling utilities such as refrigerators and air conditioners use chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs). Over time, these substances accumulate in the atmosphere and are carried by wind and wind action into the stratosphere. They are further broken up in the stratosphere and their molecules are broken up by the ultraviolet radiation from the sun which releases Chlorine atoms. The Chlorine atoms react with the Ozone, setting out a chemical cycle that destroys the good ozone. It is worthy of note that the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) estimates that once Chlorine atom can break up more than 100,000 ozone molecules.

2. The Ozone Depleting Substances (ODS)

There are also other chemical substances that are generally grouped as Ozone Depleting Substances (ODS). Examples are the methyl bromide which is often used in pesticides, methyl chloroform which is often used on making industrial solvents, and halons used in fire extinguishers. Just like the chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), these substances also do chemically react with the ozone which starts a chemical cycle that break up the good ozone.

3. Other chemicals

Other chemicals that naturally present similar reactions with the good ozone include Clx, Hox and Noy which belong to the Chlorine, Hydrogen and Nitrogen families respectively.

a. Halons-Halons which were widely used in fire extinguishers and explosion suppression system, have an extremely high potential for ozone depletion. They are ten times more potent from CFCs and they also act as global warming agent.

b. Carbon Tetrachloride (CCl₄)-Once commonly used as a cleaning agent, is an ozone-depleting chemical. It is very stable in air (lifetime 30-100 year). It can be broken down or transformed in soil and

water with several days. When it breaks down, it forms chemicals that can destroy ozone in the upper atmosphere.

c. Methyl Chloroforms – Methyl chloroform is a chemical compound consisting of carbon, hydrogen and chlorine. It was popular because of its versatility and efficiency as a solvent in cleaners, degreasers and adhesives. It was widely used by the electronics and equipment manufacturing industries. Under the Montreal Protocol its use has been banned in developed countries since 1 January 1996 and developing countries had until 2015 to do the same.

d. Methyl Bromide- It can come from natural and industrial sources. It is mainly used as a fumigant. Methyl bromide damages the ozone layer once revealed into the atmosphere. It is also toxic and harmful to humans and fauna if not used carefully. Methyl bromide breaks down relatively quickly with a half-life of about seven months

Effects of Ozone Layer Depletion

Ozone layer depletion can have some serious consequences on effects of human health, plants, ecosystems, biogeochemical cycles and earth's environment. Let us see each one of these in detail.

1. Human Health –

With depletion in ozone's layer, humans tend to be susceptible to UV rays that reaches the Earth's surface. Studies like that of Daniel, et al, (2007) suggests that high levels of UV Rays cause non-melanoma skin cancer and plays a major role in malignant melanoma development. Rozema, et al (2015) argues that Direct exposure to UV rays can lead to development of cataracts which clouds the eye's lens. Additionally, the Permanent exposure to UV rays can also lead to weakening of the response of the human immune system and even permanently damage the immune system in some cases. Finally, the Extensive exposure to UV rays can lead to acceleration of the aging process of your skin. The ozone layer act as a natural filter, stratospheric ozone depletion leads to an increase in UV radiation that causes an adverse effect on human health that are described below

a) Effect on skin-The risk for all skin types increases with exposure of UV on human immune system have been observed in people with all skin types. There are three main types of skin cancer, basal cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma and malignant melanoma. Risk of malignant melanoma has increased 10 percent.

b) Effect on the eyes – Cataracts are clouding of the eyes lens and are leading cause of permanent blindness worldwide. They are result of overexposure to UV. A sustained 10 percent thinning of the ozone layer is expected to result in nearby two million new cases of cataracts per year globally. The researchers predicted that 167, 000 to 830, 000 additional cases of cataract will be reported. Snow blindness happens when UV rays damage your eyes. The surface of your eyes is sensitive to UV rays, just like your skin. This sensitivity makes you squint in bright light to protect them.

c) DNA and UV – Exposure of UV damage to the DNA in various life forms. DNA absorbs the UV-B and changes in the DNA molecule mean that enzymes cannot “read” the DNA code results in muted cells or the cell die.

2. Plants

Ozone causes considerable damage to plants around the world including agricultural crops and plants in natural ecosystems. Ozone damages plant by entering leaf opening called stomata and oxidizing (burning) plant tissue during respiration, this damages the plant leaves and causes reduced survival. Ozone also causes a wide variety of damage in agricultural crops including visible injury, reduction in photosynthesis, alterations to carbon allocation and reduction in yield quantity and quality. High levels of ozone can inhibit a plants ability to produce chlorophyll. UV-B radiation can alter both the time of flowering as well as the number of flowers in certain species. Differences in timing of flowering may have important consequences for the availability of pollinators.

Plants become another casualty by radiation effects of UV rays. To Andersen & Sarma, (2002) the physiological and developmental processes of plants are also severely affected apart from the growth. Some other changes that are caused by UV include the way plants form, timing of development and growth, how nutrients are distributed within the plant and metabolism, etc.

3. Animal Health –

Increase in UV-B radiation that would result from significant losses of ozone is also potentially harmful to animals. The disease which are likely to increase if ozone depletion continues include the squamous cell carcinomas of the exposed, non-pigmented areas of cats, cattle, sheep and horses. Uberreuters syndrome in dogs is also associated with exposure to UV-B and may be expected to increase, as may the severity of conditions such as infections keratoconjunctivitis in cattle (Rozema, et al 2015).

4. Effect on marine ecosystems

To Andersen & Sarma, (2002) UV rays also have severe effect on the marine ecosystems. It badly affects the planktons that form the foundation of aquatic food webs. Phytoplankton grow close to the surface of the water and plays vital role in the food chain and oceanic carbon cycle. Changes in UV levels is known to affect both orientation and motility in phytoplankton. This reduces the survival and growth rate of these organisms.

UV rays are also known to affect the development stages of fish, shrimp, crab, amphibians, and other marine animals. When this happens it affects whole marine food chain as animals in the upper food chain that feed on these fishes are also affected.

5. Effect on biogeochemical cycles

Increases in UV radiation alters both sources and sinks of greenhouse gasses in the biosphere e.g.: e.g., carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, carbonyl sulfide, ozone, and possibly other gases. Changes in UV levels would contribute to biosphere-atmosphere feedbacks that mitigate or amplify the atmospheric concentrations of these gases.

6. Effect of Ozone Layer on Oceanic Life –

The effect of UV radiation on marine ecosystem is also matter of concern. Microscopic marine plants or phytoplankton, form the base food web. Dependent on sunlight for photosynthesis, phytoplankton are restricted to the upper layers of the ocean where UV-B radiation penetrates with the sunlight. Even a small decrease in phytoplankton productivity due to UV exposure could have significant effects. A decrease could be relayed through the food web and affect larvae, fish, crab, birds and mammals, which could affect the global food supply. Measurements of phytoplankton growth under increased UV concentrations due to ozone hole showed a decrease of 6 percent to 12 percent compared to normal concentrations outside the ozone hole.

Solutions to Ozone Layer Depletion

Depletion to ozone layer depletion does not affect a region or a country. In fact, whole world is vulnerable to its after affects. The increase in the levels of UV rays lead to high rate of skin cancer and eye related problems. Let's have a look at some of the solutions to ozone layer depletion.

1. Avoid products that results in ozone depletion

If you are out for shopping, don't buy aerosol products with chlorofluorocarbons. Do check your fire extinguishers if "halon" or "halogenated hydrocarbon" is the main ingredient. Dispose of old air conditioning units, refrigerators that use chlorofluorocarbons to function. This could release the toxic chemicals into the atmosphere.

2. Advocate for ozone protection

Fertilizers and pesticides are extensively used in agriculture and are also a source of nitrous oxide production which is the main culprit in depletion of ozone layer. Encourage local political representatives to raise a campaign to put forth laws governing fertilizer use.

3. Speak to your family, friends, colleagues

Ozone layer depletion is something that could prove hazardous for the entire human community. Speak to your friends, family members, colleagues and encourage them to drive less, eat local, to dispose of fire extinguishers and air conditioning units containing ODS (ozone depleting).

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this study archival research was conducted. Archival research can be used in various fields for building a reliable knowledge base (Tranfield et al., 2003). In this study, archival research provided insight on existing ozone issues by congregating available research studies. A literature review

of past ten years research (2015 to 2025) was conducted using search engines such as EBSCO, PROQUEST, JSTOR and Google Scholar. And we drew our inferences from aggregating the results of previous researches.

Key findings of the study

Based on the review of various literatures and document analysis, the findings of the study are summarized as indicated below:

1. The study found that ozone depletion arises from human activities. For instance, chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) have been considered to be the primary cause for the ozone layer depletion. They are basically from our everyday Industrial products which includes; solvents, soaps, spray aerosols, insulating foams, 'take-away' containers and cooling utilities such as refrigerators and air conditioners use chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs). Similarly, methyl bromide which is often used in pesticides, methyl chloroform which is often used on making industrial solvents, and halons used in fire extinguishers causes the depletion of the ozone layer. Just like the chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), these substances also do chemically react with the ozone which starts a chemical cycle that break up the good ozone. Other chemicals that are linked to ozone depletion include: Clx, Hox and Noy which belong to the Chlorine, Hydrogen and Nitrogen families respectively
2. The study equally found out the effects of ozone depletion has serious consequences or effects on human health, plants, ecosystems, biogeochemical cycles and earth's environment. The study observed that, with depletion in ozone's layer, humans tend to be susceptible to UV rays that reach the Earth's surface. Studies like that of Daniel, et al, (2007) suggests that high levels of UV Rays cause non-melanoma skin cancer and plays a major role in malignant melanoma development. The study is also in sync with Rozema, et al (2015) where they argued that direct exposure to UV rays can lead to development of cataracts which clouds the eye's lens. Furthermore, the study found that ozone damages plant by entering leaf opening called stomata and oxidizing (burning) plant tissue during respiration, this damages the plant leaves and causes reduced survival. For instance, UV-B radiation can alter both the time of flowering as well as the number of flowers in certain species. While on animals, the study established that, Uberreuters syndrome in dogs is also associated with exposure to UV-B and may be expected to increase, as may the severity of conditions such as infections keratoconjunctivitis in cattle (Rozema, et al 2015).
3. The study established the solutions to ozone layer depletion to include: avoid products that results in ozone depletion, advocate for ozone protection, and speak to your family, friends, colleagues and encourage them to drive less, eat local, to dispose of fire extinguishers and air conditioning units containing ODS (ozone depleting). Adhering to these measures will significantly, curb ozone layer depletion.

CONCLUSION

The Ozone layer depletion is recognized as a deep crisis which leads to increased UV radiation affecting humans and all the living organisms across the globe. Due to anthropogenic activities large amount of ozone depleting substances are released which is the main cause for ozone depletion. We can also see wide range of adverse effect in our environment. This in order to mitigate the ozone depletion issue, the whole world must join hand and spread awareness about the issue of the ozone layer depletion, so that deliberate efforts could yield positive results.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is hereby recommended that:

- 1) Avoid the consumption of gases dangerous to the ozone-layer due to their content or manufacturing process.

- 2) Minimize the use of cars – If you use a car to a destination, try to carpool with others to decrease the use of cars to pollute less and save.
- 3) Do not use cleaning products that are harmful to the environment. Many cleaning products contain solvents and substances corrosive, but you can replace these dangerous substances with non-toxic products such as vinegar and bicarbonate.
- 4) Maintain air conditioners – As their malfunctions cause CFC to escape into the atmosphere so we have to maintain our air conditioners to reduce CFC.
- 5) Buy local products – In this way you not only get fresh products but you, avoid consuming food that has travelled long distance. And which is also good for our environment.

REFERENCES

- Angell, J.K. and Korshover, J. (2005) Quasi-Biennial and Long-Term Fluctuations in Total Ozone. *Monthly Weather Review*, 101, 426-43.
- Andersen, S. and Sarma, M. (2002) *Protecting the Ozone Layer*. The United Nations History, Earthscan Publicatios Ltd., Virginia
- Andersen, S. and Sarma, M. (2002) *Protecting the Ozone Layer*. The United Nations History, Earthscan Publicatios Ltd., Virginia.
- Barnes, P. W., Williamson, C. E., Lucas, R., Robinson, S., Madronich, S., Paul, N., Zepp, R. (2019). Ozone depletion, ultraviolet radiation, climate change and prospects for a sustainable future. *Nature Sustainability*, 2(7), 569-579
- Daniel, J., Velders, G., Solomon, S., Mcfarland, M., Montzka, S. (2007). Presentand future sources and emissions of halocarbons: Toward new constraints. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 112(D2).
- Cayuela, A., Rodriguez-Dominguez, S., Lapetra-Peralta, J. and Conejo-Mir, J.S. (2005) Has Mortality from Malignant Melanoma Stopped Rising in Spain? Analysis of Trends between 1975 and 2001. *British Journal of Dermatology*, 152, 997-1000. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2133.2005.06517>.
- McMichael, A.J. (2003), (ed.), *Climate change and human health. Risk and responses*, WHO, Geneva.
- Morrisette and Peter M. (2015) *The Evolution of Policy Responses to Stratospheric Ozone Depletion*. *Natural Resources Journal*, 29, 796-797.
- Montreal Protocol (2015), from Wikipedia. Retrieved on April.01.2015 from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Montreal_Protocol
- Stephen O., E. Thomas Morehouse, Jr., & Alan Miller, (2014) “The Military’s Role in Protection of the Ozone Layer.” *Environmental Science and Technology*, vol 28, no. 13, 2014.
- Ravishankara, A.R., Daniel, J.S. and Portmann, R.W. (2009) Nitrous Oxide (N₂O): The Dominant Ozone-Depleting Substance Emitted in the 21st Century. *Science*, 326, 123-125. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.117698>
- Rozema, J., Boelen, P. and Blokker, P. (2015) Depletion of Stratospheric Ozone over the Antarctic and Arctic: Responses of Plants of Polar Terrestrial Ecosystems to Enhanced UV-B, an Overview. *Environmental Pollution*, 137, 428-442. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2005.01.048>
- Shindell, D.T., Rind, D. and Lonergan, P. (1998) Increased Polar Stratospheric Ozone Losses and Delayed Eventual Recovery Owing to Increasing Greenhouse-Gas Concentration. *Nature*, 292, 589-592. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/33385>
- Strouse, J.J., Fears, T.R., Tucker, M.A. and Wayne, A.S. (2005) Pediatric Melanoma: Risk Factor and Survival Analysis of the Surveillance, Epidemiology and End Results Database. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 23, 4735-4741. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2005.02.899>
- Sivasakthivel, T. and Reddy, K.K.S.(2011) Ozone Layer Depletion and Its Effects: A Review. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development*, 2, 30-32
- Wargent, J.J. and Jordan, B.R. (2013) From Ozone Depletion to Agriculture: Understanding the Role of UV Radiation in Sustainable Crop Production. *New Phytologist*, 197, 1058-1076. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/nph.12132>